

MAXIMUM POWER POINT TRACKING IN PV PANELS WITH CONTROL MECHANISM

*A.S.Valarmathy**V.Mahalakshmi, ***B.Ranjani, ****G.Bhuvanewari

*Associate Profesor,** Associate Professor ,Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering

**Prince Shri Venkateshwara Padmavathy Engineering CollegePonmar, Chennai

***Assistant Professor,Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering

***Prince Dr.K.Vasudevan College of Engineering & Technology, Chennai.

**** Faculty, Prince Shri Venkateshwara Arts and Science College, Gowriwakkam.

Abstract—To improve the efficiency of usage, monitoring the Maximum Power Point (MPP) of Photovoltaic (PV) modules is very critical. The P-V curve shows multiple peaks under partial shading conditions, so the purpose of the Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) techniques is to monitor the global power point and prevent local peak activity. The system is formed by a boost converter from a PV array coupled with a DC micro grid. Using MATLAB/SIMULINK, simulation results are given to determine the efficiency of the MPPT method used to track the global power point under different partial shading patterns.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE advantages of solar energy, such as air pollution free, noiseless, low maintenance and no fuel cost, have motivated power sector for taking initiatives in solar power generation on a large scale [1]. However, the only challenge with this SPV array is to extract the maximum amount of power from PV panel, because the characteristic of PV array is highly nonlinear in nature [2]. The maximum power exists only on a single point and to track or to reach that peak needs a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm. The main process of the evolutionary algorithm based MPPT algorithm is, it gets information about instantaneous voltage and current from sensors as well as it calculates instantaneous power for all searching population. After that, through internal comparison among all population decides best and worst as well as for reaching the next level updates strategy of all population. Moreover, till reaching the true MPP, this process is repeated again and again. cloud etc., the PV characteristic of the PV array consists of multiple peaks [3]. This condition is known as a partially shaded condition or non-uniformly shaded condition [2]. During this partially shaded condition (PSC), from multiple peaks [3], detection of the global peak is the main objective of the MPPT algorithm. The topmost peak is known as global maximum power point (GMPP) and rest peaks are known as local maximum power point (LMPP) [4]. A literature survey on MPPT algorithms reveals that the highly popular MPPT algorithms are perturb & observe algorithm [5], hill climbing technique and incremental conductance algorithm [6][7]. However, these algorithms are unable to track the MPP in PSC, because the principle is after reaching the first peak starts its oscillations across that peak [8]. Therefore, for searching in the entire area, the artificial intelligence based techniques are used. However, a large amount of data is required in artificial intelligence based technique, such as in neural network and in fuzzy logic algorithm [9]. Because for the training of neurones in the

neural network [10] and for fuzzification and defuzzification in fuzzy logic algorithm a huge data is required [11]. Therefore, these techniques are not suitable for the low-cost microcontroller. Hence, soft-computing based techniques are used for searching the MPP. Among various techniques, the particle swarm optimization (PSO) [12] based approach has come first, with global convergence and high-speed tracking capability. However, high-speed tracking capability due to high-velocity update sometimes creates a deviation from GMPP and slow velocity updates take longer time, as well as a huge number of iterations, are required to reach the GMPP. After that, for improvement, researchers have proposed several modified PSO [13], hybrid versions of PSO [14] (Lagrange interpolation with PSO(LIPSO) [15]), and some other evolutionary algorithms, such as modified firefly algorithm [16], firefly algorithm [17], flower pollination [18], colony of foraging ants [19], grey wolf-assisted perturb & observe [20], grey wolf optimization [21], hybrid differential evolutionary-PSO algorithm [22], etc. However, the tracking performances are not satisfactory. Then, after several modifications, Sundareswaran et al. [23] have proposed artificial bee colony (ABC) optimization algorithm for MPPT. However, during the sequential processing, its performance goes down, but it can improve by increasing the number of iterations and population size. However, this creates an unnecessary computational burden and processing delay

II. SOLAR PHOTO VOLTAIC SYSTEM

A. Modelling of Solar Photovoltaic Array

The commonly accepted solar cell model is a one diode model [24]. This paper uses the single diode model of the solar cell to model the Kyocera KC200GT solar array. This solar module is chosen in particular in order to easily validate the simulated I-V curve with the experimentally available curve from the datasheet. The detailed description of the PV array modelling and the validity of the solar panel model in MATLAB/SimPowerSystems is provided in [25].

B. PV System Configurations

The system configurations of PV with the converter/inverter interface considered for P-Q and P-V control is shown in Fig. 1. In Fig. 1(a), the inverter of PV generator is not controlled to operate at MPP but rather controlled to meet the desired active and reactive power demand as far as the capability of the PV array permits. This configuration is considered when distribution system is a part of micro grid with plenty of solar insolation but, does not have storage units, perhaps due to cost issues. In

that case, the primary objective would be to fulfil the demand through controlled dispatch of PV generators.

Fig. 1. Integrated PV system configuration. (a) P-Q control. (b) P-V control.

TABLE I
CONVERTER/INVERTER PARAMETERS

L_c	3.5mH
f_s (booster/inverter)	20kHz
L_b	0.9mH
C_b	280 mF
C_{dc}	0.2mF

The PV system is connected in parallel to the distribution grid through a coupling inductor L_c . The coupling inductor filters out the ripples in PV output current. The connection point is referred to as point of common coupling (PCC) and the PCC voltage is denoted as v_t . The rest of the system denotes the IEEE 13-bus distribution feeder which is simplified as a substation with the feeder equivalent impedance, $R_s + j\omega L_s$ and a load block to denote all the loads of the system. This simplified diagram of Fig. 1 is used for simplicity to derive the expressions of active and reactive power of the PV generator more easily as explained in Section II-C. The PV generator is connected to the dc link of the inverter with a capacitor C_{dc} . Table I shows the design parameters of dc-dc boost converter and the inverter used in the model.

This topology consists of six insulated gate bipolar transistors and antiparallel diodes each having a block voltage of V_{dc} , and three boost inductors on the ac side to compensate for the input harmonic current and to achieve a sinusoidal current waveform. In addition, EMI chokes can also be included to filter unwanted noise at switching frequency. The three phase supply from the grid is fed to PEV battery through the pair of inductors and three phase ac-dc converter. At first, PEV battery meets the active power level requested by the customer and then it supplies reactive power when demanded by the utility side.

C. Brief Review of Instantaneous Power definitions

According to the instantaneous power definitions, for a balanced three-phase system, if $v_t(t)$ and

$i_c(t)$ denote the instantaneous PCC voltage and the inverter output current, respectively, then, the average power of the PV denoted as $P(t)$, the apparent power $S(t)$, and the average non-active/reactive power $Q(t)$ of the PV are as given below [26]

$$P(t) = \frac{2}{T} \int_{t-\frac{T}{2}}^t v_t(\tau) i_c(\tau) d\tau = \frac{V_t V_c}{\omega L_c} \sin \alpha \quad (1)$$

$$S(t) = V_t(t) I_c(t) = \frac{V_t}{\omega L_c} \sqrt{V_t^2 + V_c^2 - 2V_t V_c \cos \alpha} \quad (2)$$

$$Q(t) = V_t(t) I_{cn}(t) = \sqrt{S^2(t) - P^2(t)} = \frac{V_t}{\omega L_c} (V_c \cos \alpha - V_t). \quad (3)$$

Here, $V_t(t)$ and $V_c(t)$ denote the average terminal voltage and average inverter output voltage at any time instant t . Also, $I_c(t)$ denotes the total average inverter current at time t and $I_{cn}(t)$ denotes the average non-active component of $I_c(t)$ according to non-active power theory. The detailed derivations of the equations can be found in [26].

Here, α is the phase angle of $v_c(t)$ relative to the PCC voltage. $P(t)$ and $Q(t)$ in (1) and (3) can be approximated by the first terms of the Taylor series if the angle α is small, as shown in the following

$$P(t) \approx \frac{V_t V_c}{\omega L_c} \alpha \quad (4)$$

$$Q(t) \approx \frac{V_t}{\omega L_c} (V_c - V_t). \quad (5)$$

In order to reduce power consumption, dynamic power management (DPM) techniques [28] are applied, consisting in the selective activation of the internal modules of the μC and devices of the MPPT. As the appropriate activation times are dictated by irradiance and temperature, predictive algorithms have to be used. On the other hand, the measurement and acquisition of the output current and voltage of the PV panel in order to calculate the PV power is avoided by adapting an approach proposed in [27]. This topology consists of six insulated-gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs) and anti-parallel diodes, each having a blocking voltage of V_{dc} , and three boost inductors on the ac side to compensate for the input harmonic current and to achieve a sinusoidal current waveform.

III. BACKGROUND OF CONTROL MECHANISMS

A. Architecture of Autonomous Sensors

Autonomous sensors are composed of sensing, processing, and communication stages, together with a power supply subsystem. Fig. 1 shows the block diagram of an autonomous sensor powered by a PV panel. Sensors convert a signal from a physical or chemical quantity to a corresponding signal in the electrical domain. The signal conditioning circuits match the output of the sensors to the digital processor, usually a μC . The μC processes the sensor data and controls the different blocks of the autonomous sensor. Commercial RF transceivers are used for wireless communication. An energy conditioning block, e.g., an MPPT, is used to charge in an efficient way a storage unit from the PV panel. The energy storage unit provides the demanded power to the autonomous

sensor at low or null irradianations. B. PFM Control Techniques for MPPTs The main goal of PFM control techniques consists in keeping the dc/dc converter of the MPPT in a low-power mode as long as it is possible to reduce its power consumption.

Fig. 2 shows a block diagram of such an implementation together with the temporal evolution of

Fig. 2. Block diagram of an autonomous sensor powered by a PV panel

Fig. 3. Block diagram of a PFM control technique for an MPPT and temporal evolution of some of the signals.

signals. The MPPT controller provides a suitable signal (v_m) around which the output voltage of the PV panel (v_s) will oscillate in order to work near VMPP. While the converter is in low-power mode (e.g., not switching or in shutdown), the incoming power from the PV panel charges the input capacitor (C_{in}). Then, when v_s reaches a high reference value ($v_m + V_{TH}$), the output of the hysteresis comparator toggles (shutdown signal, SHDN), and the converter activates and transfers charge to the battery at constant current (i_L). Then, C_{in} discharges until the voltage reaches a lower reference value ($v_m - V_{TL}$), placing again the converter in the low-power mode. The high and low reference values define a hysteresis window.

B. PWM control techniques for MPPTs

The main goal of PFM control techniques consists in keeping the dc/dc converter of the MPPT in a low-power mode as long as it is possible to reduce its

power consumption. Fig. 3 shows a block diagram of such an implementation together with the temporal evolution of some of the signals. The MPPT controller provides a suitable signal (v_m) around which the output voltage of the PV panel (v_s) will oscillate in order to work near VMPP. While the converter is in low-power mode (e.g., not switching or in shutdown), the incoming power from the

Fig. 4. Illustration of how the operating point of a PV panel is perturbed (ΔV_m) and the resulting power change observed (ΔP_s and $\Delta P'_s$) in a P&O method for two different operating points (v_m and v'_m).

Fig. 5. Observation and hysteresis windows with their voltage limits marked.

PV panel charges the input capacitor (C_{in}). Then, when v_s reaches a high reference value ($v_m + V_{TH}$), the output of the hysteresis comparator toggles (shutdown signal, SHDN), and the converter activates and transfers charge to the battery at constant current (i_L). Then, C_{in} discharges until the voltage reaches a lower reference value ($v_m - V_{TL}$), placing again the converter in the low-power mode. The high and low reference values define a hysteresis window.

C. P&O Tracking Algorithm

One of the most popular MPPT closed-loop methods is the P&O. Fig. 4 shows the control strategy of this method in order to reach the MPP (V_{MPP} , P_{MPP}) from two different operating points (v_m and v'_m). The algorithm slightly perturbs the operating voltage of the PV panel (ΔV_m , assumed positive) and observes how the power changes (ΔP_s and $\Delta P'_s$). If the power increases ($\Delta P_s > 0$), the operating point (v_m) will be at the left hand of VMPP and must be increased; otherwise ($\Delta P_s < 0$), the operating point (v'_m) will be at the right hand of VMPP and must be decreased. To compute power, current and voltage measurements are usually performed (Fig. 3). Current is usually sensed with a small-value shunt resistor. However, the resulting small voltage drop across the resistor has to be measured with an amplifier that presents low noise, low offset, and high gain. That raises power

loss and circuit complexity. Then, voltages are acquired by an analog-to-digital converter (ADC).

IV. CIRCUIT IMPLEMENTATION

Fig. 6 shows the circuit proposed to implement the MPPT. A MAX1795 dc/dc boost converter was used, which implements a current-limit PFM control. The MPPT controller was built around an MSP430F2618 μ C (Texas Instruments). This device combines several low-power

Fig. 6. Circuit implementation of the MPPT modes with the capability of switching the clock frequency dynamically. It also integrates modules that were used for the MPPT control such as a timer, a comparator (Comp_A+), and a 12-b digital-to-analog converter (DAC12). A digital output commanded the shutdown input (SHDN) of the dc/dc converter. The feedback terminal (FB) was wired to ground in order to select an output voltage reference of 5 V. As this value was always higher than the maximum value presented by the selected rechargeable battery (VOUT) .the converter was always switching and transferring charge whenever enabled by the SHDN control signal. A low-dropout voltage regulator (LDO1) with low power consumption was used to permanently power the μ C and an external operational amplifier (op amp) (OA_ext). An additional low-noise voltage regulator (LDO2) was used to provide the voltage of DAC12 (Vref+). This regulator presents higher power consumption and thus was only enabled (Enable signal), together with OA_ext, whenever necessary (see Section VI). As for the clocks, an internal 1-MHz clock (fDCC) was used by the CPU to run the program, whereas the timer used a 32-kHz crystal clock (fACLK) in order to perform time measurements. Three threshold voltages were used for v_s in order to operate the MPPT controller: $v_m - VTL$, $v_m - Vh$, and $v_m + Vh$ (Fig. 4). Threshold detection was carried out by using OA_ext, which processed several signals and whose output (v_o) was compared against the internal reference ($VCC/2$) of

Comp_A+. To minimize the effect of trigger noise at the input of Comp_A+, OA_ext provided some gain for v_s . As for the threshold voltages of the observation window (Fig. 4, $v_m - Vh$ and $v_m + Vh$), $v_m - Vh$ was first fixed through the output of DAC12 (VDAC), whereas the addition of $2Vh$ was achieved by changing the digital output Px (from zero to one). Another alternative was to avoid the use of Px and achieve the hysteresis variation by updating VDAC. However, this option was disregarded because the nonlinearity error of DAC12 led to an inaccurate determination of T and T and, thus, of (4), resulting in a poor tracking efficiency. Conversely, the lower value of the hysteresis window ($v_m - VTL$) was generated by updating VDAC. Now, this operation is feasible as the measurements of the charging times are not performed from this threshold voltage.

V. MPPT CONTROL STRATEGY

The classical P&O method has been implemented by using two consecutive (unperturbed and perturbed) charge cycles to calculate (4). The perturbation (ΔV_m) in the operating voltage v_m is added in the perturbed charge cycle by updating VDAC. Assuming that ΔV_m is positive, whenever (4) is positive, v_m will be smaller than VMPP and must be increased. Conversely, v_m must be decreased for negative values of (4). Taking into account this control scheme, the following control law has been proposed: $v_m(i + 1) = v_m(i) + K1((v_m(i) + \Delta V_m) T(i) - v_m(i)T(i))$ (5) where i is an integer that indicates the control cycle and $K1$ is a positive constant. A control cycle includes one unperturbed and one perturbed charge cycles. Fig. 6 shows the charge and control cycles. Sudden variations of irradiance within one single control cycle can lead to large changes in v_m when applying (5). In order to minimize these effects, a limit in the increment of v_m has been established. The values of ΔV_m and $K1$ have to be carefully selected. Large values of ΔV_m lead to large oscillations around VMPP, resulting in a decrease of the average harvested energy. On the other hand, small values of ΔV_m lead to small differences between the measured T and T. These differences can lie below the resolution of the timer, thus resulting in a larger tracking error of the MPP. Finally, a large value of $K1$ provides a fast convergence but can also lead to a large oscillation around VMPP. VI. DPM The self-power consumption of the MPPT control circuit usually limits its applicability in low-power PV panels. Table I details the power consumption estimation of each one of the modules used in the proposed implementation. Although we selected low-power components, the resulting self-consumption can represent a significant amount of the output power of the PV panel, thus wasting the energy gain obtained by the MPPT. For example, when using a 100-mW PV panel, the overall power consumption in Table I represents 3.4% of the PV panel power (at 1000 W/m²). This percentage is increased up to 20% if the average solar irradiance is taken into account [assuming that the average irradiance in Europe is 18% of its peak intensity (960 W/m²)] [19]. In order to reduce the power consumption, the system was dynamically reconfigured to activate the minimum number of modules. The premise for the successful

applicability of DPM techniques here is the smooth variations of the operating conditions of the PV panel. Under slow variations of irradiance and temperature, T and T will be similar in contiguous control cycles. Consequently, it is possible to predict when any module is needed and activate it a short time before. Fig. 7 schematically shows the time diagram of the operation of the MPPT controller in steady state. In order to save power, the CPU, DAC12, and Comp_A+ of the μC , together with LDO2 and AO_ext, are in shutdown whenever possible. The 32-kHz μC timer and LDO1 though are always active. Comp_A+ toggles whenever v_s reaches $v_m - V_{th}$ (where the timer resets), $v_m - V_h$ (instant t_1), or $v_m + V_h$ (instant t_2), generating an interrupt to the CPU. In order to make a comparison, Comp_A+, DAC12, LDO2, and OA_ext need to be activated before reaching the threshold levels. This is achieved by generating two new interrupts from the timer some prior time (t_w) before t_1 and t_2 . Overall, five interrupts that wake up the CPU and define the five states (S0 to S4) are generated. At the beginning of each state, the CPU wakes up to configure the different parts of the μC and then goes back to sleep. Comp_A+, DAC12, LDO2, and OA_ext remain active only during S0, S2, and S4. The state S1 is used to overcome the switching noise produced by the dc/dc converter during the discharge of C_{in} in S0. T is calculated as $t_2 - t_1$, where t_2 and t_1 are measured by the timer. The selected value for t_w must be long enough to account for the settling time t_s of Comp_A+, DAC12, LDO2, and OA_ext. On the other hand, t_w must be minimized to reduce the power consumption. Whenever the equilibrium point in (6) is reached, the predicted, measured, and real time values will match (t_1 and t_2 in Fig. 7). The real values $t_{j,r(i)}$ refer to the actual times when v_s crosses the threshold voltages of the observation window, i.e., $v_m - V_h$ and $v_m + V_h$. Outside the equilibrium point, whenever the modules awake early enough to detect $v_m - V_h$ and $v_m + V_h$, the real and measured values will match, and the predicted values in (6) will quickly increase toward the real values. This situation happens, for example, when the irradiation is decreasing, i.e., the charging time of C_{in} is increasing. Otherwise, the measured and predicted values will be higher than the real values. This situation happens, for example, when the irradiation is increasing, i.e., the charging time of C_{in} is decreasing. The different modules awake at $(t_{2,p(i)} - t_w)$. A similar discussion can be made about t_1 . Note that the upper limit of the hysteresis and observation windows ($v_m + V_h$) is largely surpassed, leading to a ripple increase of v_s . The slow convergence problem was solved by speeding up the decrement of $t_{j,p}$ whenever it is detected that the difference between the measured values $t_{j,m(i)}$ and the activation times $t_{j,p(i)} - t_w$ is equal to or lower than t_s . As t_s is not exactly known and is subjected to uncertainties, a higher bound t_s was selected

VI. CONCLUSION

A closed-loop MPPT μC -based implementation intended for sub watt solar panels has been proposed. Both high power efficiency and low circuit complexity have been achieved. A fast CPU clock has been used to

reduce the processing time of the implemented P&O algorithm. The MPPT algorithm accounted for a maximum CPU duty cycle of 6%. This allows using the same μC for the rest of the tasks of the autonomous sensor, such as acquiring, processing, and transmitting the sensed physical quantities. In order to reduce power consumption, DPM techniques have been applied, which implies the selective activation of the internal modules of the μC and devices of the MPPT. Predictive algorithms have been used as the appropriate activation times are dictated by irradiance and temperature. In addition, the measurement and acquisition of the output current and voltage of the PV panel in order to estimate the PV power is avoided. This skips the use of specific signal conditioners and of an ADC. Instead, the charging measuring times of a capacitor are performed by using the μC timer.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Sharma, S. P. Duttagupta and V. Agarwal, "A novel approach for maximum power tracking from curved thin-film solar photovoltaic arrays under changing environmental conditions," *IEEE Trans. Industry Applications*, vol. 50, no. 6, pp. 4142-4151, Nov.-Dec. 2014.
- [2] M. Uoya and H. Koizumi, "A calculation method of photovoltaic array's operating point for MPPT evaluation based on one-dimensional newton-raphson method," *IEEE Trans. Industry Applications*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 567- 575, Jan.-Feb. 2015.
- [3] Y. Mahmoud and E. F. El-Saadany, "Fast Power-Peaks Estimator for Partially Shaded PV Systems," *IEEE Trans. Energy Conversion*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 206-217, March 2016.
- [4] Digambar M. Tagare, "Photovoltaic EnergySolar Cells and Solar Power Systems," *Electricity Power Generation: The Changing Dimensions*, 1, Wiley-IEEE Press, 2011, pp.195-216.
- [5] M. A. Elgendy, B. Zahawi and D. J. Atkinson, "Operating Characteristics of the P&O Algorithm at High Perturbation Frequencies for Standalone PV Systems," *IEEE Trans. Energy Conversion*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 189-198, March 2015.
- [6] M. A. Elgendy, B. Zahawi and D. J. Atkinson, "Assessment of the Incremental Conductance Maximum Power Point Tracking Algorithm," *IEEE Trans. Sustainable Energy*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 108-117, Jan. 2013.
- [7] K. S. Tey and S. Mekhilef, "Modified Incremental Conductance Algorithm for Photovoltaic System Under Partial Shading Conditions and Load Variation," *IEEE Trans. Industrial Electronics*, vol. 61, no. 10, pp. 5384-5392, Oct. 2014.
- [8] I. R. Balasubramanian, S. I. Ganesan and N. Chilakapati, "Impact of partial shading on the output power of PV systems under partial shading conditions," *IET Power Electronics*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 657-666, March 2014.

- [9] A. El Khateb, N. A. Rahim, J. Selvaraj and M. N. Uddin, "Fuzzy-logic controller-based sepic converter for maximum power point tracking," *IEEE Trans. Industry Applications*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 2349-2358, July-Aug. 2014.
- [10] L. M. Elobaid, A. K. Abdulsalami and E. E. Zakzouk, "Artificial neural network-based photovoltaic maximum power point tracking techniques: A survey," *IET Renewable Power Generation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1043-1063, Nov. 2015
- [11] S. Tang, Y. Sun, Y. Chen, Y. Zhao, Y. Yang and W. Szeto, "An Enhanced MPPT Method Combining Fractional-Order and Fuzzy Logic Control," *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 640-650, March 2007.
- [12] Y. H. Liu, S. C. Huang, J. W. Huang and W. C. Liang, "A particle swarm optimization-based maximum power point tracking algorithm for PV systems operating under partially shaded conditions," *IEEE Trans. Energy Conversion*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 1027-1035, Dec. 2012.
- [13] K. Ishaque and Z. Salam, "A deterministic particle swarm optimization maximum power point tracker for photovoltaic system under partial shading condition," *IEEE Trans. Industrial Electronics*, vol. 60, no. 8, pp. 3195-3206, Aug. 2013.
- [14] K. Ishaque, Z. Salam, M. Amjad and S. Mekhilef, "An improved particle swarm optimization (PSO)-based mppt for PV with reduced steady-state oscillation," *IEEE Trans. Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 8, pp. 3627-3638, Aug. 2012.
- [15] R. B. A. Koad, A. F. Zobaa and A. El-Shahat, "A Novel MPPT Algorithm Based on Particle Swarm Optimization for Photovoltaic Systems," *IEEE Trans. Sustainable Energy*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 468-476, April 2013.